

HeriTACE

HeriTACE Website and Social Media

Deliverable D7.3

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Deliverable information

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Table of contents

Visual Identity	5
1. Logo	5
1.2. Rules when using the logo	6
1.3. Logotype.....	7
1.4. Colour palette.....	8
1.5. Typefaces.....	8
2. Project Presentation Templates	9
3. Deliverable Templates.....	9
4. Other materials.....	10

List of figures

Figure 1 - Homepage.....	7
Figure 2 - Project page	8
Figure 3 - Consortium page	9
Figure 4 - Network page	10
Figure 5 - Heritage Townhouses page	11
Figure 6 - Reports page.....	12
Figure 7 - News & Events page.....	12
Figure 8 - Media Centre page.....	13
Figure 9 - LinkedIn account	14
Figure 10 - X account.....	15

Introduction

This deliverable describes the main sections and features of the HeriTACE website, an indispensable tool for project communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement. It serves as the main channel for news and updates with the aim to address the key questions that external visitors are expected to have. The website was launched in June 2024. It will be continuously updated with news, events, communication items, deliverables, and results to keep frequent visitors and target audiences engaged. The website will evolve with the lifecycle of the project.

1. Website

The website is structured into the following main pages and subpages:

- **Homepage**, giving a glimpse of the project and the case studies, countries and duration, and containing the form to subscribe to the project newsletter and a preview of the news and events;
- **About**, containing further information on the project, the consortium, and the related initiatives and projects (such as the sister project FutureHIST and other HEU projects involving heritage buildings);
- **Heritage townhouses**, which will provide more information on the typologies of buildings selected as case studies in the future months;
- **Resources**, including the public deliverables and publications, as well as the promotional material;
- **News and event**, containing all events and initiatives in which the HeriTACE project will be involved;

The header displays three icons linking to LinkedIn, X, and the project email. It will display the YouTube icon as soon as the first videos will be available in this channel. Furthermore, a footer on all pages showcases the EU flag and a disclaimer indicating the project GA number.

ABOUT ▾ HERITAGE TOWNHOUSES RESOURCES ▾ NEWS & EVENTS

HeriTACE

Future-proofing Heritage Buildings by Optimising Comfort and Energy in Time and Space

Our transdisciplinary team, comprising research institutes, authorities, SMEs, and industry experts, is dedicated to **developing innovative solutions for deep renovations of heritage townhouses**. Through holistic assessments, optimal design approaches, durable insulation solutions, smart HVAC concepts, and integrated energy supply solutions and the use of renewable and residual energy sources, **HeriTACE ensures a sustainable future for historical neighborhoods**.

17 Partners	6 Countries	48 Months
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[Learn more](#)

Our cities

MANTOVA

Progress indicator: 1 of 4 steps active

Figure 1 - Homepage

The screenshot shows the HeriTACE project page with the following sections:

- The Project:** A header image showing a row of historic townhouses with red brick chimneys.
- Our Mission:** A text block explaining the project's goal to transform heritage townhouse buildings into energy-efficient assets while preserving their historical integrity. It mentions the EU Green Deal and the European Bauhaus.
- Objectives:** Five icons representing different goals:
 - Develop a holistic model and standard processes for renovating heritage townhouses in historical areas.
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- Key Messages:** A list of five bullet points:
 - Value for Sustainability:** HeriTACE aims to develop a balanced vision and plan for heritage buildings and neighborhoods, aligning heritage preservation with environmental goals, and providing resilient strategies and policies.
 - Deep Renovation Challenge:** The project addresses sub-optimal renovation practices responsible for historic buildings by delivering for efficient and standardized approaches to ensure coordinated execution of works.
 - Energy Efficiency and Integration:** HeriTACE focuses on significant energy demand reduction and the integration of local renewable and flexible energy sources (RES) addressing challenges in applying energy-efficient technologies and improving Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ).
 - Holistic Approach:** Emphasizing physically sound and durable insulation solutions, optimization of HVAC systems, and aesthetically integrated (P)C solutions at the neighborhood level to enhance efficiency and livability.
 - Collaborative Solutions:** HeriTACE promotes collaboration among stakeholders to develop high-quality solutions for heritage conservation, along to other existing models and standards for a sustainable energy transition in historical neighborhoods.
- Our Consortium:** A grid of logos for partner institutions including NIJKU, POLITECNICO MILANO, ghent, GENT UNIVERSITY, TAL TECH, KU, IGI, SWELT, SAKZBVT, and DENYS.
- Subscribe to HeriTACE news:** A red button at the bottom of the page.

Figure 2 - Project page

Figure 3 - Consortium page

Figure 4 - Network page

Figure 5 - Heritage Townhouses page

This page will be completed by deliverables on the cities case studies. Each town image will be clickable and allow the visitors to learn more about the methodology.

Figure 6 - Reports page

Figure 7 - News & Events page

Figure 8 - Media Centre page

2. Social Media

HeriTACE LinkedIn account

The HeriTACE LinkedIn profile has 136 followers (June 2024), including architects, engineers, experts in energy efficiency, experts in heritage buildings, researchers, and representatives for the EC. In the last six months, the page has had 176 unique visitors, 518 page views, and 4,429 overall impressions.

The KPI for social media channels is set for a combined number of 650 followers, so we are confident that we will reach this target by the end of the project.

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/heritace/>

More information can be found on D7.1.

Figure 9 - LinkedIn account

HeriTACE X account

The HeriTACE X account has 51 followers, including H2020/HEU projects. In the last 28 days, the page has reached 14 impressions and an engagement rate of 3,4%.

The consideration about the LinkedIn KPIs can be applied to X, with the target being the total number of followers of LinkedIn and X combined.

<https://x.com/HeriTACEproject>

More information can be found on D7.1.

Figure 10 - X account